

THE ROLE OF CULTURE IN LANGUAGE LEARNING PROCESS AND WAYS TO CONNECT THE CULTURE WITH EDUCATION

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6841228>

Tursunova Mashhura

English teacher at school #24 ,District Khujaobod ,region Andijan.

Annotation: *This article discusses the role of culture in language learning process and teaching cultural clues to the learners of English. Because of some cultural discrepancies, it is often difficult to adopt some materials to our own classroom. The teacher's role is very important in adjusting them and coping with this problem*

Key words. *Intercultural competence, international culture, target culture, source culture, course books, cultural tolerant.*

Introduction.

Learning language skills and its structure is not enough to be a good teacher or user of the target language. It also requires the person to be cultural competent. This comes to the top especially teaching global languages like English. It is obvious that we cannot achieve it by working individually. As a foreign language teacher, we always try to explain our learners some cultural differences and similarities. However, it is not simple or clear-cut issue like grammar or vocabulary. The key element of success in this process is not only to show the discrepancies, but also to assist learners to form intercultural competence.

Discussion

In the first place, we have to analyze the main terms related to this process such as, source culture, target culture and international culture. The term source culture identifies the culture of the person who is learning a foreign language or simply we may call it our own culture. Target culture is the culture of the country where the target language is the sole official. When we face the phrase international culture, we can analyze it by the first word "international", as it means relating to the whole world. Should we teach all types of culture? Then do we have time left to teach the language itself? The answer is "No". We do not have to teach all aspects of culture. It can be done by doing the following steps:

- The course books should include some cultural points that learners can easily capture. What is teacher's role here? Teacher should be careful in choosing the textbook and adopting it to their own class

- The activities should involve the steps that learners can feel the culture. Why I use the word "feel" here, because when teacher creates the real life

atmosphere in the classroom, students rarely forget the situation. As a result, they become cultural tolerant.

- Case studies should be included to the lessons. The role of case studies is very high in language learning process. When we give learners case studies, they are encouraged to think creatively and find solutions. This process helps them to improve both their critical thinking and intercultural competence skills.

- Using the materials describing life of celebrities in the classroom. Young learners admire celebrities, so it is interesting to learn the language through this type of material. What is the connection between celebrities and culture? Celebrities are the people who have the highest influence in development and delivery of the target culture. It is more interesting for a 15-year-old boy to learn new vocabulary by listening to his favorite song than just listening famous scientist's boring lecture.

Culture is the unique phenomenon of human being, which always changes its patterns. These changes are observed in different circumstances. Interactive classroom activities help non-native learners of English to be cultural aware and tolerant.

Conclusion

Education is an ongoing process. In order to be successful in this sphere one should always learn about new theories and be ready for any kinds of challenges. I am an ordinary schoolteacher at one of the rural areas of our country. Opportunities of children living in this place are not comparable with those in urban areas. It is difficult for this kind of a teacher to find enough sources for children and create real English atmosphere. I realize that I cannot succeed and create opportunities only by myself. We can achieve it by working in a team and assisting other teachers to create their own way. I wholeheartedly believe that the issue I am writing about interest other teachers and help their further reserches.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

1. Cook,V. (1995). Multicompetence and Effects of Age. *The Age Factor in Second Language Acquisition*. Clevedon, UK: Multilingual Matters Ltd.
2. Eli Hinkel. (2015). "Culture in Second Language Teaching an Learning". Cambridge University Press
3. Emit.M.P.J & Komesaroff.L. "Language and Learning". Oxford University Press (2003)
4. Ismail Yaman. (2017) "The role of culture in English language teaching". International Congress of Educational Research IX.

